

DEVELOPMENT OF ADAPTIVE FIBER-REINFORCED PLASTICS BY OPEN REED WEAVING TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Adaptive fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP) contain actuators that enable the controlled modification of system states and characteristics. The textile-technical integration of actuators, in particular shape memory alloys, into reinforcing fabrics has increasingly been applied in recent years. The objective is to achieve optimum force transmission from shape memory alloy to FRP, long-term stability of the adaptive FRP as well as a maximum degree of deformation. This paper presents the development of adaptive FRP, where the shape memory alloys are integrated into reinforcing fabrics by means of open reed weaving technology. After infusion of the functionalized reinforcing fabrics, the deformation behavior of adaptive FRP was electro-mechanically characterized. Results revealed that in this particular study, the maximum deformation of adaptive FRP was achieved at a voltage of 10 V and 40 s of thermal induced activation of shape memory alloys.

1 INTRODUCTION

As a result of increasingly challenging requirements in the mechanical engineering, automotive and aircraft construction industries smart materials have moved to the center of attention. This material type is characterized by the ability to actively change its physical or chemical properties, such as shape, volume, stiffness, colour or temperature. Smart materials offer advantages in terms of low space requirements, weight and wear as well as short switching times compared to classical mechanics based on additional mechanical motors, hydraulic pumps or external kinematics. Moreover, the integration of functions into the components themselves reduces the number of parts and assemblies required, thus simultaneously lowering assembly costs [1]. Adaptive fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP), a subclass of smart materials, provide these benefits, which can be used in a wide range of industries, including automotive, aerospace, and process engineering or robotic industries [2-4]. Due to the specific advantages of shape memory alloys (SMA), such as a higher usable specific energy density of $2 \cdot 10^3$ J/kg compared to other available actuator materials, e.g. shape memory polymer or piezoelectric materials, SMA is the ideal candidate for the development of adaptive FRP [5,6].

In previous research works, wire-shaped SMA that were manually integrated into FRP were investigated for the realization of adaptive FRP [7-10]. In all cases, the feasible deformation of a component equipped with these integrated actuators was comparatively small in relation to the active component length (depending on the design, a maximum of 20% was achieved). The complete textile-technical integration of SMA into FRP was not performed in these studies; instead, the SMA actuators were applied to the FRP surface. In order to ensure optimum force transmission from SMA to FRP, guarantee the long-term stability of the adaptive FRP and maximize the degree of deformation, the fully automatic textile technological integration of SMA into reinforcing fabrics is necessary [11-13].

The integration process is mainly executed by means of the weaving technology, providing high manufacturing flexibility and productivity compared to other textile techniques, such as knitting, braiding or stitching [14]. The complex in-plane 2D layout of SMA in reinforcing fabrics can be realized in a single process stage for the complex 3D deformation of adaptive FRP by means of the open reed weaving (ORW) technology. An ORW machine is a modified version of a conventional weaving machine; it is equipped with an open reed and a special shaft. Flat needles are used as thread guides in the special shaft and are coupled with a linear motor to form a sideward movement [15]. With the combined action of open reed and offset of warp yarns guided by the special shaft, woven fabrics with diagonally integrated yarns are achieved in a single process stage.

Within this research study, an adaptive FRP was developed with SMA being structurally integrated into functionalized reinforcing fabrics using ORW technology. In a subsequent step, the functionalized reinforcing fabric was infused, and finally, the thermomechanical characterization of adaptive FRP was executed.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

A market-available SMA wire (Alloy H ox. sa., Memry GmbH, Germany) with a diameter of 0.305 mm was used in this study for the development of the functionalized reinforcing fabric. This SMA is based on nickel and titanium in an atom proportion of 54.8% and 45.2%, respectively. The transition temperature, restoring force and stress of the selected SMA during the thermal induced activation of SMA were 95-110°C, 50 N and 684 MPa, respectively. The wire-shaped SMA was coated by the separating agent Dexcoat 8 (Tag chemicals, Germany) to ensure free and even mobility of SMA within FRP in order to fully exploit the deformation capability of SMA and therefore the adaption potential of the entire FRP structure. Subsequently, the coated SMA was integrated into the fabric reinforced with glass fiber (Glasseiden GmbH Oschatz, Germany). The fineness of the selected glass rovings was 1200 tex and they possessed a tensile strength of 540 according to norm DIN EN ISO 2060 and ISO 3341. In order to prevent the shape memory effect (SME) during the infusion process being an exothermic reaction, a cold-curing thermosetting matrix system was used. Hence, the commercially available resin system MGS[®] RIMR 135 was combined with the curing agent RIMH[®] 137 (Hexion, USA). In order to increase the flexibility of the matrix material, the modifier Heloxy (Hexion, USA) was mixed with the resin system at a ratio of 7:3 for the fabrication of adaptive FRP. In this case, resin and curing agent were mixed at a ratio of 10:2.4. The Young's modulus and bending modulus of the resin mixture was 1.24 GPa and 0.4 GPa, respectively.

2.2 Development of functionalized reinforcing fabrics

The functionalized reinforcing fabric was produced on a rapier weaving machine PTS 4/SOD including an ORW unit (Lindauer Dornier GmbH, Germany), as shown in Figure 1. The SMA was fed to the shedding unit by a bypass. There was a lateral offset of SMA of 20 mm, i.e. a SMA was interlaced with weft yarns every 20 mm.

Figure 1: Rapier weaving machine PTS 4/SOD with ORW function [16].

By means of interlacement between warp and weft yarns in the pliable and rigid areas, a functionalized reinforcing fabric was developed. In the pliable area, the interlacement was a plain fabric type, whereas the interlacement of the rigid area was a multilayer woven fabric in angle-interlock structure with three layers of weft yarns. Every first weft yarn was plain interwoven with warp yarns in the pliable area, while the other two floated underneath the woven fabric. The length of the pliable area of the functionalized reinforcing fabric was 50 mm. To create the pliable area in a functionalized reinforcing fabric or the hinged geometry in the final adaptive FRP, the floating yarns were cut using scissors prior to the infusion process. The developed functional reinforcing fabric is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Functionalized reinforcing fabric with SMA.

2.3 Infusion

In a next process step, the functionalized reinforcing fabric was infused by the Seemann Corporation Resin Infusion Molding Process (SCRIMP), being a variation of the Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion (VARI) Process. In preparation for the infusion process, the free end of the SMA was fixed to the reinforcing fabric by screws in order to prevent the SMA from slipping during its thermal induced activation and to generate a local force transmission area, as shown in Figure 2. The sample was cured for 15 h in a laboratory oven at 50°C to guarantee a proper cross-linking reaction between resin and hardener. After cross-linking, the sample was cut by means of a laboratory wet saw. The adaptive FRP resulting from the infusion process is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Adaptive FRP.

2.4 Electro-mechanical characterization of adaptive FRP

The deformation behavior of adaptive FRP was measured with a Keyence LJ-V7200 (Keyence, America) laser triangulator. The data storage rate of the laser triangulator during measurements was 10 Hz. Laboratory power supply units of type BT (Basetech, Germany) were used for the activation of SMA in adaptive FRP. In this experiment, the power supply was set to up to 10 V at 2 V increments. The voltage was controlled by using a microcontroller board (LilyPad). In this research study, the cycle time was varied from 10 s to 60 s at time increments of 10 s. For the realization of different cycle times, an Arduino development environment was selected to program the microcontroller. The total duration for each experiment was 1500 s.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An example deformation curve of adaptive FRP activated by 10 V/ 2A current over the entire measurement period with a heating and cooling cycle of 40 s each is shown in Figure 4. This figure reveals that adaptive FRP deforms due to the phase change of SMA from a martensite to an austenite state during its thermal induced activation.

Figure 4: An example deformation curve of the adaptive FRP.

The maximum deformation of the adaptive FRP depending on the applied voltage is plotted in Figure 5. According to the presented voltage range, there is an exponential relationship between maximum deformation and electrical voltage. This figure shows that during the thermal induced

activation, the adaptive FRP reaches its maximum deformation at 10 V due to the phase transition temperature of integrated SMA from a martensite to an austenite state achieved by this voltage.

Figure 5: Exponential relationship between voltage and maximum deformation of the adaptive FRP.

The deformation speed of the adaptive FRP by varying the time is shown in Figure 6. Similar to the deformation behavior, the deformation speed of adaptive FRP increases by increasing the voltage. Here, the deformation speed is higher during the heating cycle than during the cooling cycle. This can be attributed to the active heating caused by energy and the passive cooling due to ambient temperature.

Figure 6: Deformation speed of adaptive FRP by varying voltage.

The maximum deformation of adaptive FRP with variable activation times from 10 to 60 s is shown in Figure 7. Results reveal that the maximum deformation of adaptive FRP increased linearly with the activation time from 10 s to 40 s. The maximum deformation of adaptive FRP at an activation time of 50 s is reduced compared to 40 s. This phenomenon results from the generated heat accumulation of SMA in adaptive FRP for a prolonged period reducing the SME of SMA. A similar

effect is also reported in Ref. [17], where the maximum deformation was achieved at 60 s of thermal induced activation of SMA in a core-sheath structure.

Figure 7: Maximum deformation of adaptive FRP in dependence on activation time.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The development and electro-mechanical characterization of adaptive FRP have been discussed in this paper. The functionalized reinforcing fabric for the development of adaptive FRP was realized based on ORW technology. The maximum deformation of adaptive FRP in this study was achieved by a voltage of 10 V and 40 s of thermal induced activation of SMA. The pre-competitive knowledge generated within the framework of this study can be used for the design and manufacture of adaptive FRP, e.g. in robotics (e.g. as manipulators, gripping tools), orthotics (joint replacement and biokinematics, exoskeletons) and prosthetics (limb replacement).

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